

Azine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Titrations with Chloramine-T†

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NEUTRAL Red¹ is the only azine dye that has been reported as a redox indicator in titrations of As^{III} and Sb^{III} with chloramine-T (CAT). In this communication, we present the results of our investigations on the use of six azine dyes, phenosafranine (PS), methylene violet (MV), amethyst violet (AV), safranin-T (ST), Wool Fast Blue BL (WFBBL) (Colour Index Nos. 50200, 50210, 50225, 50240 and 50315, respectively) and aposafranine (AS), as redox indicators in titrations of As^{III}, Sb^{III}, hydroquinone, ascorbic acid, hydrazine and isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) with CAT in neutral and hydrochloric, sulphuric and acetic acid media.

Experimental

Approximately 0.1 N solutions of CAT, Sb^{III}, hydrazine, hydroquinone and INH were prepared and standardised. Standard solution (0.1 N) of As^{III} and 0.1% solutions of the dyes in deionised water, were also prepared. The following dye samples were used, PS, MV, AV, ST and AS (Gurr) and WFBBL (Bayer). Other chemicals used were of reagent grade quality.

General procedure: An aliquots of the reductant solution (0.1 or 0.025 N) was treated with sufficient 1 : 1 hydrochloric, sulphuric or acetic acid and water so as to give the required overall acidity when diluted to 50 ml. A 0.1% indicator solution (0.1 ml) was then added and the mixture titrated with CAT solution, potassium bromide solution being added wherever necessary. The conditions of titrations and colour changes at the end-points are given in Table I. The results obtained are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

Determination of ascorbic acid and INH contents in pharmaceutical preparations: The developed indicator methods were applied for the determina-

TABLE I—TITRATION CONDITIONS AND END-POINT COLOUR CHANGES

Reductant	Indicators	Medium and end-point colour change
As ^{III} ^a	PS, ST and AS	Neutral ^c ; pink to colourless
	WFBBL	Neutral or 1M HCl ^c ; light blue to colourless
Sb ^{III} ^a	PS ^b , ST and AS	Neutral ^d ; pink to colourless
	MV and AV	Neutral ^d ; pinkish violet to colourless
	WFBBL	Neutral ^d ; blue to colourless
Hydroquinone	WFBBL	Neutral ^d ; pale blue to green
Ascorbic acid	PS	Neutral ^c or 1.0–2.0 M HCl ^c ; violet to light pink
	MV, AV and ST	Neutral ^c ; pink to colourless
	AS	Neutral ^c ; pink to violet
	MV	1.0–2.0 M HCl ^c ; pinkish violet to pink
	AS	1.0–2.0 M HCl ^c ; violet to light pink
	WFBBL	Neutral or 1.0–3.0 M acetic acid ^c ; light blue to colourless
	Hydrazine ^a	PS and ST
	WFBBL	0.5–1.5 M HCl; blue to colourless
INH	ST and AS	1.0–2.0 M HCl; pale pink to colourless
	WFBBL	Neutral; blue to colourless

^aIndicator correction of 0.1 ml has to be applied in titrations of 0.025 N solutions. ^bNot suitable for titrations of 0.025 N solutions. ^c+1 ml of 0.1 M KBr solution. ^d+1 ml of 1 M KBr solution.

tion of the ascorbic acid and INH contents of commercial pharmaceutical preparations as per the following procedure. One tablet of the preparation was ground into a fine powder, dissolved in deionised water, filtered through a G4 sintered glass funnel, washed and the filtrate diluted to 100 ml. In the case of ascorbic acid, a known volume of the solution was treated with 0.1 M KBr solution (1 ml) and a 0.1% solution (0.1 ml) of PS, MV, AV, ST, WFBBL or AS, diluted to 50 ml, and the mixture titrated with 0.1 N CAT solution until the colour changes mentioned in Table 1 were obtained. A similar aliquot was titrated with CAT solution using starch as indicator² for the sake of comparison. The procedure was repeated with different commercial samples of vitamin C tablets. The results obtained are in very good agreement with those obtained with starch as indicator.

In the case of INH, an aliquot of the solution prepared from the tablet, was treated with enough 1:1 HCl to give an overall acidity of 1 M when diluted to 50 ml, and one drop of 0.1% ST, WFBBL or AS, and the mixture was titrated with 0.1 N CAT solution till the colour changes mentioned in Table 1 were obtained. The results obtained are in very good agreement with those obtained with quinoline yellow as indicator³.

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Emission Spectrographic Estimation of Silver, Bismuth, Molybdenum and Vanadium in Soil and Rocks

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An emission spectrographic procedure is described for the estimation of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in parts per billion levels in soils and rocks. The sample is attacked by aqua regia and the above elements are adsorbed on activated charcoal, which is ashed, and the four elements are estimated by measuring their respective spectral intensities.

Experimental

Preparation of samples: The sample (10 g) powdered to 200 mesh was spread evenly in a flat-

bottomed (3" dia) porcelain dish and roasted in a muffle furnace at 400° for 1 h. It was cooled, transferred to a 400 ml beaker and freshly prepared aqua regia (20 ml) was added. The sample was then digested for 4–5 h on a water-bath with stirring, and demineralised water (250 ml) was added, stirred well, and left overnight. The solution was filtered through Whatman no. 40 filter paper into a 500 ml beaker and the residue on the filter paper was washed 4–5 times with demineralised water, making sure that no residue passed into the filtrate. The filtrate was diluted to 400 ml with demineralised water. Into the filtrate, A.R. quality activated charcoal (0.5 g of 200 mesh) was added and stirred for 20 min with a magnetic stirrer. The solution was then filtered through a Whatman no. 41 filter paper and the filtrate rejected. The filter paper containing the charcoal was carefully placed in a 30 ml flat-bottomed porcelain crucible and kept in a muffle furnace. The temperature of the furnace was slowly raised to 550° and maintained for ~1.5 h till the contents of the crucible were completely converted into ash. Access to air should be allowed during the ashing of the charcoal in the muffle furnace.

Preparation of standards: Specpure samples of oxides of Ag, Bi, Mo and V were weighed and mixed thoroughly in an agate pestle and mortar with a pegmatite base (I) so as to make a final concentration of 1000 ppm of each element. Pegmatite base was prepared by mixing together 60 parts of 200 mesh quartz (specpure) with 40 parts of 200 mesh spectrographically screened microcline and 1 part of iron oxide (specpure). Further dilutions of the standard were made with pegmatite base as per Table 1, so as to form

TABLE 1—DILUTIONS MADE TO PREPARE STANDARD SOLID SOLUTIONS

Content of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in the initial solid solution	Quantity of the initial solution taken	Quantity of Pegmatite base mixed	Final quantity of the solid solution	Ag, Bi, Mo and V content in the final solid solution
1000	1.0	9.0	10.0	100
100	1.0	9.0	10.0	10
10	1.0	9.0	10.0	1
1.0	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.1
0.1	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.01
0.01	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.001

a series of standard solid solutions with concentrations of 100, 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01 and 0.001 ppm. Each standard was thoroughly mixed to make sure the homogeneity of the sample. Each standard (10 g) was weighed into a 250 ml beaker and aqua regia (20 ml) added. All the steps adopted for the samples were followed for the standards to obtain the spectrum of the four elements. By a visual comparison of the intensity of the spectrum of the four elements in the unknown sample with